

Rapid Assessment of Calcined Clay Reactivity for Strength Prediction in LC³ Systems

Sandra Mujombi ^{1,2,3}, Yujia Min ², Elsa Qoku ³, Thomas Matschei ³,
Nishant Garg ², Wilson R. Leal da Silva ¹

¹ Fuller Technologies, Denmark

² University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, USA

³ Institute of Building Material and Research, RWTH Aachen University, Germany

Corresponding author: smu@flsmidth.com

Abstract

Understanding the reactivity of calcined clays is critical for their application as supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) in low-carbon cements. Despite recent advancements in reactivity testing, existing methods are constrained by long evaluation times, limiting their industrial use. This study develops an integrated test framework that combines complementary reactivity tests to predict the 28-day compressive strength of cementitious composites produced with limestone calcined-clay cement (LC³). To quantify these reactivity contributions, the intrinsic dissolution potential of the calcined clays was assessed using the UR² test, which quantifies dissolved Al and Si concentrations in 5-15 minutes. Aluminate-sulfate interactions were evaluated in a clinker-free model system by determining sulfate depletion time from isothermal calorimetry, and early pozzolanic reactivity was measured using the 24-hour cumulative heat release from the R³ test. These methods were applied to four natural clays calcined at 600 and 800 °C. For the studied clays, all results were obtained within a 24-hour experimental period and incorporated into a multi-variable regression model fit for 28-day strength prediction. Altogether, the proposed integrated test framework enables rapid assessment of calcined clay reactivity and prediction of 28-day strength from data obtained within 24 hours, supporting faster material screening and quality control in industrial settings.

Keywords: calcined clay; quality control; rapid screening; reactivity; compressive strength.

1. Introduction

Transitioning towards low carbon cements requires efficient utilization of Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs) that can partially replace Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) without compromising mechanical performance, specifically the 28-day compressive strength. Numerous studies have shown that calcined clays are particularly promising SCMs due to their wide availability and strong pozzolanic potential [1]. However, their contribution to strength development in blended cements depends strongly on their mineralogy, degree of dehydroxylation and fineness amongst other factors [2]. Therefore, reliable prediction of calcined clay reactivity is essential to support optimized processing and formulation of blended binders.

Despite notable advancements in reactivity testing, standard evaluation methods e.g. the R^3 test (7 days) and Strength Activity Index (SAI - 28 days) require 1-4 weeks for completion, delaying material qualification. At an existing industrial flash calciner production scale (ca. 1250 t/day) [3], such testing durations delay feedback, limiting the frequency of quality verification and increasing the risk that variations in feed or calcination conditions go undetected over production volumes on the order of 10^4 to 10^5 t. By delivering reactivity data in a short time frame, rapid methods can provide real time feedback that support immediate adjustments to SCM processing and enable optimization of composite cement blends despite inherent raw material variability.

Recent developments have introduced accelerated reactivity tests capable of probing specific reaction mechanisms relevant to hydration in LC^3 cementitious systems [5], [6], [7]. The UR^2 test [5] captures the dissolution process of alumina (Al) and silica (Si), the principal reactive constituents in calcined clays, which dissolve partly or fully under alkaline conditions depending on the intrinsic characteristics of the clay [8].

The R^3 test defined in [6] measures the cumulative heat released by an SCM after 7 days in a standardized clinker-free environment. In the present work, the 24-hour cumulative heat fraction from the same procedure is used as an indicator of the clay's contribution to early pozzolanic reactivity, consistent with previous work, showing a correlation between 24-hour heat release from the R^3 test and early age strength for kaolinitic clays [9]. A positive correlation was also observed in the present dataset.

The clinker-free model system, also referred to as the sulfate-limited model system (SLiM) tracks gypsum consumption in a system containing an excess of an alumina-rich SCM, portlandite and a limited sulfate source (gypsum) [7], quantifying the reaction rate of alumina-bearing phases when sulfate is the limiting reagent. Each of these tests isolates critical aspects relevant to strength development. However, when used in isolation, they provide fragmented insights into a process governed jointly by dissolution, pozzolanic reaction, and the evolution of sulfate phases.

The central hypothesis of this work is that the combination of these reactivity metrics provides a predictive descriptor for 28-day strength in LC^3 -50 systems. Rather than evaluating these metrics independently, the present approach integrates the UR^2 , 24-hour heat release (R^3) and SLiM parameters into a single linear regression model, referred to here as an integrated reactivity framework (Fig. 1). For the clays evaluated in this study, all three measurements are obtained within 24 hours, enabling prediction of 28-day compressive strength after one day of testing and rapid screening of calcined clays for use LC^3 -type systems.

Fig. 1. Integrated reactivity framework combining UR^2 , 24-hour heat release (R^3), and SLiM parameters.

2. Materials and Methods

Four natural clays used in cement production were thermally activated by calcination. Thermogravimetric analysis was used to identify dehydroxylation peaks and two temperatures within the optimal range (i.e. after the dehydroxylation peak) 600 and 800 °C were selected (Fig. 2). The raw clays were calcined at the chosen temperatures in a muffle furnace for 60 minutes and then cooled naturally. The resulting samples (n=8) are labelled C1-4, with the suffix 6 or 8 indicating calcination at 600 or 800 °C.

Fig 2. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) curves of the raw clay samples (C1-C4)

The chemical composition was determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) using a PANalytical Zetium spectrometer (Malvern Panalytical), the results are shown in Table 1. The instrument operates with a rhodium anode X-ray tube rated up to 4 kW, at 60 kV and 125 mA, equipped with a beryllium (Be) front window and a detector system comprising flow proportional, scintillation, and Xe sealed detectors. Samples were prepared as glass disks by fusion with lithium borate.

Table 1. Chemical and mineralogical composition of the raw clays (C1-C4).

Oxide (wt%)	C1	C2	C3	C4
SiO ₂	58.65	61.49	48.80	70.24
Al ₂ O ₃	24.56	18.52	19.31	17.39
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.09	7.70	16.34	3.52
CaO	1.09	0.02	0.12	0.02
MgO	0.11	0.49	0.89	0.01
Mn ₂ O ₃	-	-	0.18	0.02
TiO ₂	0.31	0.95	2.94	1.63
P ₂ O ₅	-	0.13	0.27	0.05
K ₂ O	0.46	3.88	0.49	0.17
Na ₂ O	-	0.01	-	-

Table 1 (continued).

Oxide (wt%)	C1	C2	C3	C4
SrO	-	-	-	0.01
SO ₃	0.18	-	-	0.03
LOI, 950°C	11.65	6.87	10.73	7.14*
XRD phases (%)				
Kaolinite group	63.90	25.00	55.00	33.40
Illite	1.50	20.10	7.90	-
Quartz	34.20	47.60	29.00	66.60
Fe-bearing phases	0.40	7.30	8.10	-

* Loss of ignition (LOI) for C4 was determined at 975°C

The mineralogical composition of the clays (Table 1) was investigated by X-ray diffraction, (XRD) using an Empyrean diffractometer (Panalytical) with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda_1 = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$, $\lambda_2 = 1.5444 \text{ \AA}$), operating at 40 kV and 15 mA.

The following reactivity tests were carried out:

- **15-min UR² test (UR² Index):** The release of Al and Si ions in alkaline solution was determined by dissolving the calcined clay in 4M NaOH at 90°C, following [5]. Aliquots were collected after 15 minutes, filtered, diluted, and the Al and Si concentrations were measured by colorimetry using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer; the 15-minute dissolution time was selected because it provided improved prediction accuracy for 28-day compressive strength for the clays studied. For all eight samples, the test was performed in triplicate. Concentrations derived from absorbance measurements were used to calculate the dissolution index (1.54Al + Si). The reported UR² index values (R, -) were normalised by dividing each measured index by the maximum index obtained across all samples.
- **R³ test:** Heat release of the calcined clays was investigated using the R³ isothermal calorimetry method [6]. The heat flow was measured for 7-days at 40°C for the eight samples; however, only the 24-hour cumulative heat was used for this study (R³_{24h}, J/g).
- **Clinker-free model system (SLiM):** The clinker-free model system [7] was used to determine the early reaction kinetic of the clays. Eight mixtures containing calcined clay, portlandite and gypsum (74: 18.5: 7.5 by mass) were prepared to determine the sulfate-source depletion time (t_{s_cDT}), i.e. the time associated with the second heat flow peak in the calorimetric curve. Sulfate-source depletion times were expressed as their reciprocal, 1/t_{s_cDT} (h⁻¹) The test was conducted at 25°C.
- **Compressive strength test (LC³-50 formulations):** LC³-50 mortars served as the reference system for assessing how the rapid reactivity metrics predict 28-day mechanical performance. Pastes containing 52.5% clinker, 30% calcined clay, 15% limestone and 2.5% gypsum (by mass of binder) were prepared using water-to-binder ratio of 0.5 and a superplasticizer dosage of 0.4% by weight of binder. The mixtures were cast into (19 × 19 × 144) mm (height × width × length) mini-RILEM prisms[10], sealed with a steel plate, demoulded after 24 hours, and stored at 20°C until testing.

Compressive strength was measured at 28-days (f_{c28} , MPa) for 8 mortar mixtures. Three replicate samples were tested per mixture (24 samples total). The reported values are the average of the three replicates per mixture.

A multi-variable regression model, Eq. (1), was fitted to predict the 28-day compressive strength of LC³-50 mortars as a function of reactivity parameters described above.

$$f_{c28} = C_0 + C_1UR^2 + C_2R_{24h}^3 + C_3\left(\frac{1}{t_{ScDT}}\right), \quad (1)$$

The linear regression model constitutes the integrated reactivity framework, in which the dissolution capacity (UR^2), early heat release (R_{24h}^3), and the aluminate-sulfate reaction kinetics ($1/t_{ScDT}$) are used as independent predictors of compressive strength. The approach enables the three-reactivity metrics to be combined into a single performance indicator obtainable within 24 hours. The coefficients C_0 to C_3 were obtained by the least square method. The coefficient of determination and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to quantify the quality of the fit.

3. Results and Discussion

The R_{24h}^3 (Fig. 3a) served as proxy for early pozzolanic reactivity. Increasing the calcination temperature from 600 °C to 800 °C enhanced the reactivity of all clays, although the magnitude of this effect was clay dependent. The increase was most pronounced for C1 which contains dickite, a polymorph requiring higher temperatures for complete dehydroxylation compared with kaolinite [11]. In contrast, C2 displayed the lowest heat release, consistent with the lower reactivity of illite phases [12].

Fig. 3. Reactivity indicators for C1 to C4: (a) 24-hour cumulative heat release from the R^3 test, (b) reciprocal sulfate source depletion time (h^{-1}), and (c) 15-min normalized UR^2 index.

The reciprocal sulfate source depletion time ($1/t_{ScDT}$), which represents the rate of sulfate consumption (higher values correspond to faster depletion), is shown in Fig. 3b. Samples with a high R_{24h}^3 also exhibit high $1/t_{ScDT}$ values, indicating that both tests

capture complementary aspects of early reactivity of calcined clays, even though the underlying reaction mechanisms differ. C4 exhibits the highest $1/t_{\text{SeDT}}$ values at both calcination temperatures indicating faster early reaction kinetics. As this test indirectly measures Al release, which is inversely proportional to sulfate consumption, the results confirm that this clay rapidly released Al, accelerating ettringite formation. In contrast, the presence of illite and Fe-bearing phases in C2 and C3 led to slower dissolution kinetics and delayed sulfate consumption.

The 15-min UR^2 index (Fig. 3c) indicates that C1 and C4 have the highest dissolution potential at both 600 and 800 °C. For C1, this corresponds to its high kaolinite content. C4, however, shows comparable reactivity despite containing only ca. 33% kaolinite, indicating efficient activation of its reactive phase during calcination. This behaviour is consistent with prior work showing that reactivity depends on activation efficiency, structural disorder, and accessibility of reactive sites rather than on kaolinite content alone [13,14]. Consistent with this, C3 shows intermediate reactivity, reflecting the influence of Fe-bearing phases that limit the available amorphous aluminosilicate. C2 shows the lowest UR^2 index due to its low kaolinite content and high illite and quartz fractions which are less reactive phases. This aligns with the observations from [5], who similarly reported a low dissolution potential for an illitic clay. The minimal increase between 600 and 800 °C for clays C3 and C4 suggests that further calcination did not enhance the UR^2 index.

Fig. 4. Measured versus predicted 28-day compressive strength for C1-C4 calcined at 600 °C and 800 °C ($R^2 = 0.9585$). Error bars show the standard error between replicate tests for measured values.

The linear regression model, Eq. (1), developed to predict the 28-day compressive strength ($f_{c,28}$) of $\text{LC}^3\text{-50}$ mortars showed a strong linear correlation between measured and predicted values, with an R^2 of 0.9585 (Fig. 4). The fitted coefficients were $C_0 = 19.535$, $C_1 = 17.623$, $C_2 = 0.028$, and $C_3 = 85.605$, corresponding to the intercept, UR^2 index, R^3_{24h} , and $1/t_{\text{SeDT}}$ respectively. The model combined the R^3_{24h} as an indicator of early pozzolanic reactivity, the reciprocal t_{SeDT} , reflecting aluminate-sulfate

reaction kinetics, and the 15-min-UR² index reflecting the intrinsic dissolution capacity of the calcined clay. Together, these parameters highlight the complementary nature of the three tests. The linear regression captured strength variations across both calcination temperatures, demonstrating that the combined use of these rapid tests captures reactions that govern strength development. Overall, the model provides a quantitative basis for rapidly screening calcined clays for LC³ applications.

The contour map in Fig. 5 was generated from Eq. (1) by interpolating across the experimental range of UR² indexes and R³_{24h} values, while fixing 1/t_{ScDT} at its mean value. The plot provides a visual representation of how changes in the rapid reactivity metrics influence the predicted 28-day strength. This demonstrates that, within 24-hour, these metrics can provide quantitative estimates of 28-day strength in LC³-50 systems.

Fig. 5. Contour plot showing the predicted 28-day compressive strength as a function of the 15-min normalized UR² index and R³_{24h}.

The integrated reactivity framework bridges rapid reactivity metrics and long-term mechanical performance, reducing the testing duration from several weeks to 24 hours, thereby enabling efficient quality-control screening. However, validation using a broader range of clays with different mineralogical compositions and calcination conditions is recommended to confirm the general applicability of the approach. In addition, duplicate measurements would allow thorough statistical evaluation and increase the robustness of the predictions, given the variability in both clay properties and calcination conditions. Cross-validation across different binder compositions would further strengthen the applicability of the approach.

4. Summary

In this work we propose an integrated reactivity framework in which the use of the UR², R³, and SLiM tests provide complementary reactivity metrics, and their integration in a linear regression model enables accurate prediction of 28-day compressive strength (R² = 0.9585) in an LC³-50 system. This integrated reactivity framework links mechanistic

descriptors from heat evolution, aluminate-sulfate reaction kinetics and the available reactive aluminosilicate species to strength development, offering a more comprehensive assessment than any single test alone. The strong correlation between the combined rapid reactivity metrics and 28-day strength demonstrates that material qualification can be achieved within one day of testing. This outcome has direct industrial relevance, supporting rapid screening, process optimization, and the development of formulation tools for low carbon binders.

Future work should verify the applicability of the integrated reactivity framework across a wider set of clays and binder formulations, while incorporating replicate measurements and variations in calcination conditions to establish prediction reliability under production conditions.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge the support from the project “Data Enabling Transformation and Optimization towards Concrete Sustainability” (DETOCS) that is funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101119929. Funded by the European Union - views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them.

References

- [1] K. Scrivener, F. Martirena, S. Bishnoi, and S. Maity, “Calcined clay limestone cements (LC3),” *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 114, pp. 49–56, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2017.08.017.
- [2] R. Jaskulski, D. Józwiak-Niedźwiedzka, and Y. Yakymchko, “Calcined Clay as Supplementary Cementitious Material,” *Materials*, vol. 13, no. 21, 2020, doi: 10.3390/ma13214734.
- [3] Heidelberg Materials, “Scaling up low-carbon clinker alternatives: World’s largest calcined clay plant in Ghana starts production,” May 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.heidelbergmaterials.com/en/pr-2025-05-16>
- [4] S. Bishnoi, S. Maity, A. Mallik, S. Joseph, and S. Krishnan, “Pilot scale manufacture of limestone calcined clay cement : The Indian experience,” *Indian Concrete Journal*, vol. 7, pp. 22–28, July 2014.
- [5] Y. Min, H. Kabir, C. Kothari, M. F. Iqbal, and N. Garg, “UR2: Ultra-rapid reactivity test for real-time, low-cost quality control of calcined clays,” *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 191, p. 107806, May 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2025.107806.
- [6] *ASTM C1897-20: Standard Test Methods for Measuring the Reactivity of Supplementary Cementitious Materials by Isothermal Calorimetry and Bound Water Measurements*, C1897-20. doi: 10.1520/C1897-20.
- [7] T. R. Muzenda, Y. Demeusy, F. Georget, C. Labbez, and T. Matschei, “Sulfate adjustment and early reactivity in cements containing kaolinitic calcined clays: investigation and assessment via a sulfate-limited model system,” *Cement and*

Concrete Research, vol. 199, p. 108060, Jan. 2026, doi:
10.1016/j.cemconres.2025.108060.

- [8] F. Zunino *et al.*, “Hydration and mixture design of calcined clay blended cements: review by the RILEM TC 282-CCL,” *Materials and Structures*, vol. 55, no. 9, p. 234, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1617/s11527-022-02060-1.
- [9] F. Avet, R. Snellings, A. Alujas Diaz, M. Ben Haha, and K. Scrivener, “Development of a new rapid, relevant and reliable (R3) test method to evaluate the pozzolanic reactivity of calcined kaolinitic clays,” *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 85, pp. 1–11, July 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2016.02.015.
- [10] I. Pol Segura, P. A. Jensen, and W. R. Leal da Silva, “Effect of activation technologies on natural clays reactivity,” *Journal of Sustainable Cement-Based Materials*, pp. 1–18, doi: 10.1080/21650373.2025.2573671.
- [11] M. Izadifar *et al.*, “Comprehensive examination of dehydroxylation of Kaolinite, disordered Kaolinite, and Dickite: Experimental studies and density functional theory,” *Clays and Clay Minerals*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 319–333, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s42860-020-00082-w.
- [12] R. Fernandez, F. Martirena, and K. L. Scrivener, “The origin of the pozzolanic activity of calcined clay minerals: A comparison between kaolinite, illite and montmorillonite,” *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 113–122, Jan. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.cemconres.2010.09.013.
- [13] C. Ramadji, A. Messan, S. O. Sore, E. Prud’homme, and P. Nshimiyimana, “Microstructural Analysis of the Reactivity Parameters of Calcined Clays,” *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 4, 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14042308.
- [14] S. Overmann, A. Vollpracht, and T. Matschei, “Reactivity of Calcined Clays as SCM—A Review,” *Materials*, vol. 17, no. 2, 2024, doi: 10.3390/ma17020312.